

THE DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROGRESS: INDUSTRIAL REFORM**I.A. Hajiye***Doctor of Art (Dr. Sc.),**Professor Azerbaijan Technological University**Full member of the Turon Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan,**full member of the Russian Academy of Natural Sciences.*

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Abstract

The presented article discusses the role of design in the socio-cultural development of the society at the modern stage, as well as traditional practices and development perspectives related to this field of activity. According to the demands and laws of the constantly changing economic conditions in the global space, the design of new types of consumer goods at the level of modern standards should be noted as one of the important tasks facing design and creative activity. On the other hand, traditional production areas, for example, used to exist in local conditions in Azerbaijan. One of the fields of artistic production, kalaghayi - the production of women's headdress samples in new technological processes can not only affect the development of the textile industry in the republic, but also ensure the access of those samples to the world markets. These products based on silk raw materials, which are completely appropriate from an ecological point of view, will create a basis for displaying these products in a wide space as brand goods. Of course, the implementation of this or that process of activity in this direction is directly related to the work of professional staff training, which is discussed in the article.

Keywords: design, industry, textile, technology, tradition, future, education, personnel training

Introduction

The term design has been used since the middle Ages. In English, the word "design" began to spread since the 16th century. In the same period, many new discoveries, inventions, and various examples of creativity appeared, which in a certain sense are also characterized as design achievements. The outstanding representative of the Renaissance, Leonardo da Vinci (1452-1519), has the essence of inventions ahead of his time, amazing creative ideas, and design-projecting activities.

The word "design", which is literally translated from English, expresses the words "plan", "painting", "drawing", unlike other fields of art, was formed precisely in the conditions of accelerated industrialization. In this sense, it is more emphasized that it belongs to the industrial art development in various countries of Western Europe.

In Europe, the development of industry, including technical progress, formed a new technical thinking and aesthetic outlook in the society, unlike traditional art. This created the foundation for the formation of technical aesthetics as a certain direction and the emergence of various scientific theories in this field. Finally, at the end of the 19th century in England, the German architect G. Zemper (1803-1879), the English art critic J. Ruskin (1819-1900) and the English artist and public figure U. Morris (1834-1896) appeared in the example of the original design theories, which created conditions for fundamental development of industrial aesthetics, technical aesthetics, design in general - industrial art on a scientific-theoretical basis. Therefore, experts attribute the history of the development of design on a scientific-theoretical basis to that period.

Analysis

The preparation of items', devices' and equipment' samples, in accordance with international norms related to the activity and development of agricultural fields, large industrial enterprises, as well as the production of various samples of household items and equipment for various purposes by the conveyor method are important issues facing the design activity today. In addition to these, the problems of creating comfortable conditions that can ensure comprehensive human activity in the context of ergo esthetic factors in the organization of *human-object-machine-environmental* systems are also solved by design.

Considering the variety of design areas, in this case, it is necessary to pay attention to its broad classification by direction. It should also be noted that the classification is constantly expanding due to the emergence of new areas of activity in design. Even in the 1970s, the design was mostly limited in a few directions (Kagan, 1972), in the current period, it is necessary to look at this field of creativity in a wider aspect.

At the modern stage, directions in design are defined according to the classification given below:

- industrial design (all kinds of light and heavy (including military) industrial goods);
- graphic design (publishing-polygraph, logo, emblem, letterhead, etc.);
- computer design;
- animation design;
- transport design;
- architectural design (architectural buildings, monuments, interior and exterior);
- landscape design (greening zones – park, garden, alley, etc.);
- ecological design;
- ornament design;

- textile design;
- accessory and clothing design;
- art - design;
- futurodesign etc. (Hajiyev, 2020).

As can be seen from the classification, design in modern conditions has become a global field of activity and covers various spheres of activity. This field of activity based on the practice of artistic and technical creativity, like design culture, penetrates the latest achievements of scientific technologies and mutually benefits from them (the possibilities of technological processes), and at the same time provides the experience of creating new alternatives of samples based on existing prototypes. Thus, design - projecting provides the practical implementation of innovative ideas in the organization of *human - object - machine - environment* systems, and creates a foundation for the development of scientific - technical progress, design culture. Of course, this, as a result, provides the social and cultural needs of the society and leads to the improvement of its standard of living and well-being. Design, which is an artistic-technical design activity, benefits from the possibilities of modern scientific achievements, as well as, if necessary, the most modern computer programs.

The continuous development of the industrial sector in the countries throughout the world, the revival of the economy in Azerbaijan requires the creation of new production enterprises, as well as the creation of a new variety of products in accordance with modern requirements. From this point of view, it is necessary to share experiences at an international level on design, to cooperate with the leading countries of the world both in the field of education and production - from time to time to hold scientific seminars, conferences and other events and meetings.

It should be noted that such practices and traditions used to exist in the field of design in Azerbaijan, even during the Soviet times. One of the influential events was a special international design seminar called "Interdesign-83" organized in Baku in 1983 under conditions of wide cooperation under the All-Union Technical Aesthetics Science and Research Institute. The exchange of experience in the scientific-practical, artistic-aesthetic, and social aspects of the seminar can be characterized as achievements in design creativity in the republic. The holding of this seminar of international importance, which is the 15th in number, in Baku once again confirmed the acquisition of professional-level personnel potential in the republic, as well as certain experience in design creativity. 24 specialists (14 - USSR, 2 - Hungary, 2 - GDR, 2 - Czechoslovakia, 4 - Japan) took part in the seminar lasting 2 weeks (October 4-18). The work of the seminar was led by Y.B. Solovyov, director of the main institute, R.M. Hasanov, director of the branch, and other specialist (Hajiyev 2021).

The main purpose of the seminar held on the topic of design for rural life was to work out the design process for various areas of rural influence, as well as settlements as an experiment. Azerbaijani artists, specialists in design Shahin Alasgarov, Vadim Kogan, Kamal Muradov, Alexander Putnikov, Sanan Salamzade and

Rahim Seyfullayev as well as representatives of various nationalities, took part in that seminar.

Giving preference to such experiences in the new context of modern times, of course, can have a significant impact on the scientific and practical development of design activity, which is one of the important creative fields in the republic. Of course, for the realization of this development process, it is important to have a base that can guarantee scientific-theoretical and practical activities of leading enterprises conditioned by modern requirements. This includes the activities of scientific and educational institutions, as well as enterprises engaged in production activities. Suggestive and recommended ideas related to these parables are periodically included in various publications, including conference materials.

Wide investigation of the problems and research papers related to design and creative activity in our republic, plus suggestions and recommendations in this direction, were systematically included in a short cultural and analytical periodical called "Creation of design and innovations centre" (Jafarov & Agazade, 2017).

The proposals and recommendations highlighted in this article can be considered acceptable at one or another level, and they can be benefited at a certain level in the development of various directions of design in the republic.

There are factors that ensure the social and cultural development of the society and the improvement of the general well-being of the population in every era, which are realized directly by the creation of new and modern technologies and their successful application in various fields of the industry. As it mentioned in the cited source, since 1992, the independent Azerbaijan Republic signed trade agreements on a number of industries and has been trading with the member-countries of the Economic Cooperation and Development Organization in clothing, food, leather, shoes, rubber and plastic, computers, electronic items and optical products, machinery and various purposes equipment, pharmacy, printing materials and textile industries (Jafarov & Agazade, 2017). These contracts, which were concluded at a multifaceted level, naturally affected the dynamics of the development of various fields of the textile industry in the republic in line with international standards. We should especially mention that the main part of this development was the result of design and creative activity. Of course, the future sustainable development of these traditions, which have been increasing since the independence period in the republic, is highly dependent on the effective organization of professional personnel training. In the educational institution where the authors of the article are engaged in pedagogical activities, the constant improvement of the works related to the mentioned issue and, as a result, the training of professional designer personnel are in the focus of special attention.

One of the development areas of the general industry in Azerbaijan can be characterized by the development of the textile, fabric and clothing industry based on rich production traditions both in the Soviet times and in the current conditions. In addition to these,

kalaghayi - decorative women's headdresses made of special silk fabric based on the local production process have also formed a part of the national textile industry.

Kalagayi production has been known in Azerbaijan since ancient times. It is known from written sources that high-quality kalaghayis were made in the cities of Tabriz, Ganja, Shamakhi, Sheki, and Nakhchivan. In the Middle Ages, there were small enterprises that produced kalaghayi in the territories of Azerbaijan. Although kalaghayi were previously made individually, later special enterprises producing kalaghayi started to operate. It should also be noted that at the

meeting of UNESCO's Intergovernmental Committee on Intangible Cultural Heritage held on November 26, 2014, the art of Azerbaijan kalaghayi "Kalaghayi symbolism and traditional art" was included in UNESCO's Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage. According to the well-known fashion designer Fakhriyya Khalafova, who has repeatedly used kalaghayi in her clothing collections, kalaghayi must be modernized for mass use, and new kalaghayi samples should be released for production. <https://az.wikipedia.org/wiki/>

Figure 1. Samples of kalaghayi made of Azerbaijani silk.

Samples of kalaghayi made in Sheki (Figure 2; 3). It should be noted that these traditions are continued even in the current conditions.

a)

b)

Figure 2; 3. Samples of kalaghayi made in Sheki.

Methods and methodology

In connection with the transition to the market economy, the artistic design of products produced in light industries, including textiles (cloth, knitwear, carpets, clothing, shoes, leather haberdashery, etc.) is of special importance. The design of the products is one of the factors that make it suitable for modern taste, as well as one of the important factors that bring economic efficiency. Currently, the development of textile mass-production requires the strengthening of international relations and the expansion of scientific and technical information exchange. This leads to the development of international socio-cultural relations and meeting the unified international standards and benchmarks in quality and aesthetic levels of the products. Of course, by using advanced methods, modern techniques and technologies in the artistic design of the product, it is possible to bring it to the world markets as a high-quality commodity.

It is known that the social importance of this or any other issue depends on giving it any form according to the purpose. Of course, industrial art does not express the social essence alone. Since the products are created within the framework of the social or economic system, they are the carriers of the signs of the system and are directly dependent on the social demand. The product, being beautiful in shape and appearance, should also be useful as a carrier of a certain function. The theory of artistic design is formed on the basis of social requirements and mainly determines the following:

- addressing models by studying prints and copies;
- learning the forms of construction of elements in nature, architecture and technology;
- studying people's historical and ethnographic traditions;
- studying the structural possibilities of the form and information about its pre-construction;
- research of various indicators (requirements and conditions) on utilitarian-functional and ergoesthetic factors in shaping;
- analysis of modern technology and technical possibilities with the aim of inverting the artistic ideas in industrial production;

- determining the location of the planned object (Mirzoev & Hajiyeve, 2024).

Conclusion

The development of cocooning and sericulture, which has a rich history and experience in Azerbaijan, at a new stage, based on new technological processes, will create a foundation for the mass production of colorful kalagayi-women's headdresses based on silk raw materials, which are part of the textile industry. Such samples will attract the attention of a large number of buyers in both domestic and foreign trade centers due to their attractive decoration and, especially, in contrast to other raw materials, due to their higher hygienic quality. We can say with certainty that the designer-specialists we have prepared for the textile industry will make their worthy contribution to the development of the industry in the republic in the near future with their activity and abilities, to the creation of competitive brand products that can be placed in the world markets.

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